

Review

Efficacy of Acupuncture in the Symptoms of the Carpal Tunnel Syndrome: Assessment of Efficacy and Methodologies.

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Abstract: Carpal Tunnel Syndrome (CTS) is a compressive neuropathy of the median nerve at the wrist, most prevalent in adults aged 40 to 60, predominantly affecting women. Characterized by symptoms such as tingling, pain, and numbness in the upper extremities, CTS negatively impacts quality of life and work capacity. Conventional therapies—both surgical and conservative—have limitations, underscoring the need for a multidisciplinary approach.

This study explores acupuncture's role in CTS management from the perspective of Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM). In TCM, CTS is viewed as a Painful Obstruction (*bi*) Syndrome related to external factors—wind, cold, and dampness. Pathologically, CTS arises from stagnation of *Qi*, Blood, and Phlegm, often coupled with deficiencies in *Qi*, *Yin*, *Yang*, or Blood.

Literature reviews and clinical trials support acupuncture's efficacy in pain relief and symptom improvement. Acupoint selection (e.g., PC 7, PC 6) is grounded in TCM theory to restore energetic balance and enhance circulation. Complementary *Tuina* massage further reduces inflammation and promotes mitochondrial biogenesis.

Although evidence is promising, further high-quality studies are needed to consolidate acupuncture's benefits in CTS. Integrative approaches combining acupuncture and *Tuina* present a valuable alternative for improving functionality and quality of life in CTS patients, offering symptomatic relief and potentially reducing reliance on conventional treatments.

Keywords: Carpal tunnel syndrome; Traditional Chinese Medicine; Acupuncture.

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1. Background

CTS is a compressive neuropathy of the median nerve at the wrist and is the most common entrapment neuropathy ¹. It predominantly affects adults between 40 and 60 years old, is five times more common in women than in men, and is very rare in children ². CTS manifests as symptomatic compression of the median nerve, with primary symptoms of tingling, pain, and/or numbness in the areas innervated by that nerve—the thumb, index, middle finger, and radial half of the ring finger—as well as reduced strength and function of the affected hand ³.

Common conservative treatments include local corticosteroid injections, musculoskeletal manipulation, and immobilization ⁴. However, corticosteroid injections provide limited long-term benefit—approximately three-quarters of patients require surgery within one year ⁵, and evidence for splinting's effectiveness is inconclusive ⁶.

Surgical release of the transverse carpal ligament remains the most definitive intervention to alter the relationship between the median nerve, tendons, and carpal tunnel ⁴. Yet surgery carries risks of nerve, arterial, or tendon injury; complex regional pain syndrome; scarring; transient neuropraxia; and potential reoperation ^{7,8}.

Given conventional therapies' limitations and CTS's impact on an active population, there is a critical need for therapeutic options that offer durable symptom relief.

TCM is a holistic medical system that understands health as a state of cooperative functioning among biological systems, which can be negatively affected when disrupted⁹. Currently, the evidence base for TCM supports its use as part of integrative medicine, offering a potentially beneficial approach when incorporated into healthcare systems by enhancing clinical outcomes, patient quality of life, and access to care⁹.

Acupuncture, as a TCM technique, is defined by the insertion of fine needles at specific points or areas of the body¹⁰. Its aim is to promote an enhanced state of well-being through regulation of the nervous, circulatory, endocrine, and exocrine systems¹¹. Although the mechanisms of acupuncture remain incompletely understood¹², its benefits extend across numerous areas of human health including mental health^{9,13,14}, gastrointestinal disorders¹⁵⁻¹⁸, gynecological conditions¹⁹⁻²¹, and pain management²²⁻²⁴, among many others²⁵⁻³³.

Accordingly, the primary objective of this study is to elucidate the effects of acupuncture in the treatment and management of CTS. We also examine CTS through the lens of TCM and outline the specific therapeutic approaches employed in acupuncture.

2. Traditional Chinese Medicine and Acupuncture in Carpal Tunnel Syndrome

2.1. Carpal Tunnel Syndrome from the TCM Perspective

In TCM, CTS falls under the category of Painful Obstruction Syndromes (*bi*). “*bi*” signifies blockage causing pain, numbness, or sensitivity in muscles, tendons, and joints, and is attributed to invasion by external Wind, Cold, or Dampness³⁴.

Chronic *bi* may involve stagnation of *Qi*, Blood, and body fluids; development of Phlegm; and ultimately Blood stasis, further impeding circulation and intensifying pain.

However, according to Fredes et al.³⁵, Classical TCM texts describe six pathological causes of paresthesia, ranging from nerve impulse transmission failure to chronic injury and *Qi*/Blood deficiency, each correlating with specific citations in the Huangdi Neijing (Inner Canon of the Yellow Emperor). These can be observed in Table 1.

Table 1. Reasons for the Appearance of Paresthesia. Adapted from Fredes et al.³⁵.

Failure in the transmission of nerve impulses.	Failure in the movement of defensive energy.	“Puncture for the regulation of the genuine and the evil. In: Gan ZW, Wang XY, editors. <i>The spirit axis of the inner canon of the divine Yellow Emperor</i> . Beijing: Xue Yuan Press; 2016. p. 183.” ³⁶
Poor nutrition and failure in blood irrigation.	“When the nutritive <i>Qi</i> is empty, there is numbness.”	“Discussion of the inverted regulation. In: Gan ZW, Wang XY, editors. <i>The spirit axis of the inner canon of the divine Yellow Emperor</i> . Beijing: Xue Yuan Press; 2013. p. 164.” ³⁷
Chronic injury to the nervous and circulatory systems.	“When there is no pain, but there is swelling, the disease has remained and deepened. The circulation of nutritive and defensive <i>Qi</i> is rough, and the channels and collaterals occasionally relax. In this way, they are obstructed. There is a lack of nutrition in the skin. Thus, there is numbness.”	“Discussion of block [disease]. In: Gan ZW, Wang XY, editors. <i>The spirit axis of the inner canon of the divine Yellow Emperor</i> . Beijing: Xue Yuan Press; 2013. p. 207.” ³⁸
Neurasthenia.	“When the body is frequently frightened and fearful, the tendons and vessels are obstructed, generating numbness.”	“Discussion of the nine needles. In: Gan ZW, Wang XY, editors. <i>The spirit axis of the inner canon of the divine Yellow Emperor</i> . Beijing: Xue Yuan Press; 2016. p. 194.” ³⁹
Diabetes.	“When there is heat in the <i>Qi</i> of the Spleen-pancreas, the stomach dries out, and there is	“Discussion of atrophy [disease]. In: Gan ZW, Wang XY, editors. <i>The spirit axis of the inner</i>

	thirst. There is numbness in the muscles and flesh, manifesting as flesh atrophy.”	<i>canon of the divine Yellow Emperor. Beijing: Xue Yuan Press; 2013. p. 208.”</i> ⁴⁰
Prolonged contraction from cold.	“When cold and <i>bì</i> (blockage) become diseases and are retained without being eliminated, there is occasionally pain and numbness in the skin.”	“Longevity, die early and the strong and the soft. In: Gan ZW, Wang XY, editors. <i>The spirit axis of the inner canon of the divine Yellow Emperor. Beijing: Xue Yuan Press; 2016. p. 24.”</i> ⁴¹

Moreover, tendinous atrophy (including nerves) may arise from inflammation (Heat) and inadequate nutrition (Dryness), with specific channel involvements (*Tai Yin, Yang Ming, Jue Yin* of the hand) detailed in classical sources³⁵.

In the case of neuropathies, nerve damage is precisely described as a “tendon injury” (as one of the “Five Bodies” (五體 *wǔ tǐ*) – tendons and membranes). Table 2 presents the reasoning of Fredes et al.³⁵ regarding the development of tendon atrophy and neuropathies associated with CTS.

Table 2. Development of Tendon Atrophy and Neuropathies Associated with CTS According to TCM. Adapted from Fredes et al.

³⁵.

Tendon Atrophy – Heat and Dryness	“When there is heat in the Liver <i>Qi</i> , the Gallbladder drains, the mouth is bitter, and the tendons and membranes dry out. When the tendons and membranes dry out, the tendons become tense and contract, manifesting as tendon atrophy”	“Discussion of atrophy [disease]. In: Gan ZW, Wang XY, editors. <i>The spirit axis of the inner canon of the divine Yellow Emperor. Beijing: Xue Yuan Press; 2013. p. 208.”</i> ⁴⁰
Neuropathies – Tendon Injury (tendons in classical Chinese medicine = Connective, muscular, and nervous tissues or tendino-muscular channels)	Possible injury in: Tai Yin channel of the hand (lung) Yang Ming channel of the hand (large intestine) Jue Yin channel of the hand (pericardium)	“The tendons of the channels. In: Gan ZW, Wang XY, editors. <i>The spirit axis of the inner canon of the divine Yellow Emperor. Beijing: Xue Yuan Press; 2016. p. 51.”</i> ⁴²

2.2. Acupuncture for Carpal Tunnel Syndrome

Regarding the application of acupuncture for CTS, Branco e Naeser⁴³ conducted a study using several non-pharmacological approaches, including acupuncture and laser therapy. They observed complete pain reduction in 50% of the cases. At the follow-up, 1 to 2 years later, only 2 of the 23 treated hands (8.3%) experienced a recurrence of pain, which resolved quickly within a few weeks of renewed treatment. The authors noted that these results were associated with increased blood flow to the brain, particularly to the thalamus. Possible mechanisms identified include increased cellular adenosine triphosphate (ATP), reduced inflammation, and a temporary rise in serotonin levels.

Similarly, Yang *et al.*⁴⁴ compared the effects of acupuncture using Pericardium 5 and Pericardium 6 points in the treatment of CTS with oral prednisolone. They found that by the end of the treatment period, improvements were similar in both groups, except for the symptom “waking during the night due to symptomatology,” which showed more significant improvement in the acupuncture group.

In line with this, Cai⁴⁵ conducted a study to investigate the effectiveness of acupuncture combined with *Tuina* massage in 98 patients with CTS. The results showed that acupuncture together with *Tuina* manipulation produced highly significant therapeutic effects.

Carlson *et al.*⁴⁶, in their examination of various non-surgical therapeutic options for managing CTS symptoms, reported that 38% of the American population turned to so-called complementary therapies for pain management.

Evidence supporting the effect of acupuncture in improving CTS symptoms was also noted by Prime *et al.*⁴⁷, who found that acupuncture significantly improved the function of the median nerve.

Confirming these findings, Khosrawi *et al.*⁴⁸ carried out a controlled, randomized study to assess the efficacy of acupuncture in treating mild to moderate CTS. Patients underwent eight acupuncture sessions, compared to a control group that received four weeks of nighttime hand splinting, vitamin B1 and B6 supplementation, and sham acupuncture. The authors concluded that acupuncture can improve overall subjective symptoms and should be considered in the care plans of these patients. The acupuncture points used in the study were PC 7 and PC 6.

Another study showing positive results with acupuncture in CTS was conducted by Ho *et al.*⁴⁹, concluding that acupuncture had a therapeutic effect, particularly in improving symptoms, grip strength, and electrophysiological function.

Furthermore, Hadianfard *et al.*⁵⁰ conducted a randomized study involving 50 participants, comparing various therapeutic options for CTS. They found that patients who received acupuncture showed better outcomes in pain reduction compared to those who used ibuprofen. In addition to pain, they also saw greater improvements in tingling and numbness. The acupuncture group also reported fewer nighttime awakenings due to pain or other symptoms related to CTS.

Chung *et al.*⁵¹ also highlighted in their literature review that acupuncture is widely used in Chinese medicine for treating pain and neuropathy. The authors presented results from a 2011 systematic literature review that included two studies comparing acupuncture with local steroid injections. These showed that the acupuncture group had more significant improvements in reducing CTS symptoms compared to those who received steroid injections. They also referenced another randomized study from 2009, which showed that patients treated with acupuncture had better outcomes than those who took low doses of oral corticosteroids.

A recent clinical study by Fredes *et al.*³⁵ demonstrated that acupuncture can yield significant results in CTS patients, particularly in reducing pain intensity – potentially increasing pressure pain thresholds by an average of 0.682 kgf/cm². Daytime and nighttime paresthesia also improved significantly, as did functional impairments related to decreased strength caused by CTS.

However, referring to the most recent systematic review and meta-analysis by Dong *et al.*⁵², the findings were as follows:

Compared to night splinting, acupuncture alone was more effective in relieving pain. However, no significant differences were observed in symptom severity or functional status.

Acupuncture alone may be as effective as medication in improving symptom severity and electrophysiological parameters.

As a complementary treatment, acupuncture may have beneficial effects on symptom severity, functional status, pain intensity, and electrophysiological parameters. When combined with medication, acupuncture showed superior outcomes compared to medication alone.

There is still a lack of high-quality studies to draw definitive conclusions.

Thus, according to these authors, acupuncture has the potential to be beneficial as an adjunct treatment for CTS.

Overall, based on the evidence reviewed in this section, further studies are needed to confirm the beneficial effects acupuncture may offer in treating CTS.

2.3. Therapeutic Approach in Acupuncture

Fredes *et al.*³⁵, in their clinical study, selected several foundational acupuncture points based on the logic of classical Chinese medicine and aligned with the results previously discussed. Table 3 presents a summary of these:

Table 3. Channels affected in CTS and points applied to all patients

Tai Yin Channel of the Hand	"Broken Sequence" (LU 7 列缺 <i>Liè Quē</i>)
Jue Yin Channel of the Hand	"Great Mound" (PC 7 大陵 <i>Dà Líng</i>)
Yang Ming Channel of the Hand	"Union of the Valleys" (LI 4 合谷 <i>Hé Gǔ</i>)

In their study, other points were also selected individually for each case, depending on the patient's specific concomitant imbalances. These are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Concomitant imbalances and applied acupuncture points

Imbalance	Acupuncture Points
Liver Blood deficiency; Liver <i>Qi</i> stagnation	<i>Qū Quán</i> (LIV 8), <i>Dà Dūn</i> (LIV 1), <i>Sān Yīn Jiāo</i> (SP 6)
Liver Blood deficiency; Liver <i>Qi</i> stagnation; Spleen-Pancreas and Kidney <i>Qi</i> deficiency with damp retention	<i>Qū Quán</i> (LIV 8), <i>Dà Dūn</i> (LIV 1), <i>Sān Yīn Jiāo</i> (SP 6), <i>Tài Bái</i> (SP 3), <i>Yīn Líng Quán</i> (SP 9), <i>Fù Liū</i> (KI 7)
Liver <i>Qi</i> stagnation; Spleen-Pancreas <i>Qi</i> deficiency	<i>Gān Shū</i> (BL 18), <i>Tài Chōng</i> (LIV 3), <i>Tài Bái</i> (SP 3), <i>Yīn Bái</i> (SP 1)
Liver Blood deficiency and Blood stasis; Spleen-Pancreas <i>Qi</i> deficiency	<i>Qū Quán</i> (LIV 8), <i>Dà Dūn</i> (LIV 1), <i>Tài Bái</i> (SP 3), <i>Sān Yīn Jiāo</i> (SP 6), Bleeding and cupping at <i>Gé Shū</i> (BL 17)
Liver Blood deficiency and Blood stasis	Acupuncture and moxibustion at <i>Qū Quán</i> (LIV 8); Moxibustion at <i>Dà Dūn</i> (LIV 1); Acupuncture and moxibustion at <i>Sān Yīn Jiāo</i> (SP 6); Bleeding and cupping at <i>Gé Shū</i> (BL 17); Bleeding at <i>Qū Chí</i> (LI 11)

In this study, based on the table above, we observe two main approaches were used: (1) Local — to directly treat the affected area, and (2) Distal — to regulate the underlying syndromes observed in each patient.

In another study by Napadow *et al.*⁵³, local acupuncture was applied to the affected hand or distally at the ankle. Both approaches improved nerve signaling. However, the advantage of local acupuncture was particularly noted in cortical remapping, which translated into longer-term benefits.

The most recent systematic review mentioned earlier⁵² reported the frequency of acupuncture point usage across 16 included studies, as illustrated in Figure 1.

From this data, we can observe that the most frequently used acupuncture point in CTS research is PC 7. In second place, used in 75% of the studies, is PC 6. Third place is held by LI 4 and LI 11, both applied in 50% of the studies.

The anatomical locations of these points, according to the World Health Organization⁵⁴, are shown in Figures 2, 3, 4, and 5.

Figure 1. – Frequency of acupuncture point usage according to Dong *et al.* ⁵².

Figure 2. PC 7

Figure 3. PC 6

Figure 4. LI 4

Figure 5. LI 11

2.4. Acupuncture and Tuina Massage

The main objective of *Tuina* massage is to remove energy blockages that lead to *Qi* stagnation. This massage aims to increase the circulation of *Qi* and blood and reduce localized edema, which in turn helps relieve pain. The painful area is usually where the energetic and blood blockages are located. Therefore, manipulating these points promotes the free flow of *Qi* and improves blood circulation in the affected region⁵⁵. The authors cite studies showing that one of the mechanisms through which *Tuina* massage provides benefits is by reducing inflammation and promoting mitochondrial biogenesis, which contributes to the repair of damaged skeletal muscle tissue.

To demonstrate the effectiveness of *Tuina* massage in pain reduction, we highlight the findings of Lewis *et al.*⁵⁶, who analyzed 20 studies involving a total of 1,341 participants. Their aim was to assess the effect of therapeutic massage on pain control. Nine of these studies were conducted on healthy individuals, where the interventions were intended to reduce post-exercise pain. The remaining 11 studies involved patients with musculoskeletal disorders whose symptoms included pain. Therapeutic massage was shown to be effective in reducing pain in half of these 20 studies. Of the nine studies conducted on healthy individuals, four showed improvement in pain conditions. In the group of patients with musculoskeletal disorders, six studies also reported positive outcomes compared to the control group. However, the authors noted that small sample sizes, poor methodological quality, and short massage duration led them to consider the results inconclusive.

In a separate study, Tsao⁵⁷ conducted a systematic review and found that patients with CTS who received *Tuina* massage for four weeks (15 minutes per day) showed improvements in pain, grip strength, anxiety, and depression compared to the control group.

Likewise, Cai⁴⁵ carried out a study (previously mentioned in this paper) to evaluate the effectiveness of acupuncture combined with *Tuina* massage in 98 patients with CTS. It

was found that the combination of acupuncture and *Tuina* manipulation had very significant therapeutic effects.

Jiang et al. (2016) confirmed these conclusions in their randomized study involving 98 individuals with CTS, divided into two groups: a treatment group and a control group. The treatment group received acupuncture at specifically selected points followed by *Tuina* relaxation massage, while the control group received conventional pharmacological treatment. The results revealed a statistically significant difference between the groups ($P < 0.01$), with the treatment group achieving a cure rate of 81.7% compared to 47.4% in the control group. This led to the conclusion that acupuncture combined with *Tuina* massage may be a simple yet effective therapy for CTS.

Following the promising findings of the previous studies, a recent study by Chen et al.⁵⁸ examined the effects of electroacupuncture combined with *Tuina* on the median nerve conduction velocity and joint motor function rehabilitation in patients with CTS. In this study, the treatment group received electroacupuncture combined with *Tuina*, while the control group received conventional medication. The overall efficacy rate in the treatment group was 95.24%, significantly higher than the control group's 78.57%. Symptom and functional scores in both groups significantly decreased after treatment, with the treatment group showing significantly lower scores than the control group post-treatment.

Furthermore, after treatment, the range of motion for radial deviation, ulnar deviation, dorsal extension, and palmar flexion significantly improved in both groups. Sensory conduction velocity from the thumb and middle finger to the wrist, as well as motor conduction velocity from the thenar muscle to the wrist, also significantly improved in both groups. However, the wrist joint range of motion and median nerve conduction velocity were significantly higher in the treatment group than in the control group. Pain scores in both groups also significantly decreased after two weeks and one month of treatment, with the treatment group showing significantly lower pain scores. Recurrence rates after six months and one year were significantly lower in the treatment group compared to the control group.

According to the results of this study, treatment with electroacupuncture combined with *Tuina* for CTS can improve wrist joint range of motion and median nerve conduction velocity. Additionally, it effectively relieves pain, improves wrist motor function, and reduces clinical recurrence rates.

These promising results further highlight the importance of applying acupuncture within an integrated context of traditional Chinese medicine techniques—specifically, in conjunction with *Tuina* massage.

In this context, it would also be beneficial to explore the application of other traditional Chinese medicine techniques, either in combination with acupuncture or as stand-alone treatments. Examples include cupping therapy⁵⁹⁻⁶² or even traditional phytopharmacology⁶³⁻⁶⁶.

3. Conclusions

In TCM, CTS is a Painful Obstruction (*bi*) Syndrome linked to Wind, Cold, and Dampness, leading to *Qi*, Blood, and fluid stagnation. Neurovascular and tendon atrophies are explained by classical channel pathologies.

Clinical evidence generally shows significant pain reduction, improved nerve function, and enhanced circulation with acupuncture—particularly at PC 7 and PC 6—both locally and distally. Combining acupuncture with *Tuina* or conventional therapies offers additional benefits, though more high-quality studies are warranted.

Overall, integrative approaches grounded in TCM theory hold significant potential to improve quality of life for CTS sufferers and may reduce dependence on invasive or pharmacological interventions..

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